

Research Article

Antecedents and Outcome of Electronic Word of Mouth (EWOM): Moderating Role of Product Involvement

Muhammad Arslan Sarwar¹, Zainudin Awang^{2*}, Jawaria Nasir³, Ibrahim Tijjani Sabiu⁴, Rossidi Usop⁵, and Siti Fariha Muhamad⁶

1 Affiliation ¹; arslanjatala@hotmail.com

2 Affiliation ³; javeyrianasir@yahoo.com

3 Affiliation ⁴; ibraits@yahoo.com

4 Affiliation ⁵; rossi_sidi@yahoo.com

4 Affiliation ⁶; fariha@umk.edu.my

* Correspondence: zainuddinawang@unisza.edu.my

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Abstract: In this competitive world, the consumers are now becoming less attentive and aware towards traditional ways of advertising so that's why many companies are now focusing to reduce spending toward commercial advertising and diverting more toward the word of mouth promotions. For this reason, electronic word of mouth eWOM is under the constant consideration of academicians and practitioners. Seeing the importance of eWOM in recent times the current study seeks to model the antecedents and outcomes of eWOM. Specifically, this study examines the impact of source credibility, message appeal and brand equity on purchase intentions through eWOM. A survey questionnaire is used to test the said objectives. Data is collected from 224 mobile users with the help of convenient sampling. In general, the results of the study are in favor of the validation of measures and proposed rational paths. This study offers empirical evidence which may provide solid grounds for practical implications

Keywords: Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM); Source Credibility; Message Appeal; Brand Equity; Mobile Phone Industry.

About the Authors

Prof. Dr. Zainudin bin Awang from Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin Malaysia (left in picture) is a renowned research scholar also appointed as a trainer and research consultant at many private organizations. He has written many books in his area of specialization. Among the books are Structural Equation Modeling, Quantitative Business Analysis, Business Statistics, Research Methodology & Data Analysis, and Guides in Writing a Research Proposal. Muhammad Arslan Sarwar (right in picture) is Ph.D. Scholar in Faculty of Economics & Management Sciences, Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin and Assistant Professor

Public Interest Statement

The Internet has allowed people to have better information as a consumer and exchange of information between consumers. At present, consumers are looking for a lot of information on the Internet before making any decision. Among the multiple information available, the comments and opinions of other consumers are the most valued. Consumer-to-consumer (C2C) communication in social media has become a critical element for companies, especially for mobile phone brands. The importance of C2C communication has made it fundamental to analyze the causes of electronic Word-Of-Mouth (eWOM). It has a major impact on

in University of Gujrat, Pakistan working on branding, consumer behavior and marketing communication strategies.

customer decision making. We will analyze this in this paper how it can affect people choice.

1. Introduction

Consumers of modern ages are now becoming less attentive and less aware about traditional advertising as many companies have focused to decline to spend toward commercial advertising and diverted toward the word of mouth campaigns" (Kilby, 2007). The Word of mouth defined as one to one verbal contact or communication between buyers that may contain a source of information regards a product or service, and when such communications or information sharing turns on electronic media than it becomes the electronic word of mouth communication. The electronic sharing platform can be social networking sites, blogs, other websites or other electronic media channel (Park, Lee & Han, 2007). Electronic word of mouth (EWOM) is known as the trading of learning and data by different buyers who utilize a similar scope of items. In eWOM noncommercial publicizing led by customers who have coordinates understanding of the particular item and its effect on the acquiring choices of different shoppers (Park, Lee & Han, 2007). The present study uses the mobile phone industry key players to generalize the results as the most of ads and conversation on social media about cell phone brands like Nokia, Samsung, HTC, I phone and Blackberry are becoming popular. Generally, individuals use to share their involvement in the type of messages via web-based networking media about the mobile phone in a positive or negative way. While WOM articulation in any case identified with the idea of the talk among purchasers in regards to various items, the worldwide spread of web advertising is making this an all-inclusive correspondence by overhearing people's conversations less close to home shape for both sender and beneficiary, so this is known as EWOM communication (Xia et al., 2008)

Consumers think that credibility of WOM message is more effective than traditional advertising that's why the influence of WOM is greater than other commercial advertisements. The credibility of message source has a high impact on believe of the consumer in the message, it means that consumer where from acknowledging the information about the product that should be credible for him to further enhance the purchase intention of that product.

Brand equity is known as an extra value or some special utility assigned to a brand name by the brand manufacturer discussed by the (Yoo & Donthu, 2001). This brand equity has a positive and significant impact on the attitude of the customer while purchasing that particular brand and also on various organizational outcomes for instance marketing efficiency, stock price and market achievement of that brand discussed by the (Keller, 1993; Yoo & Donthu, 2001).

Those customers who are having a high level of product or brand association are more conscious regarding the information about that brand/product and they also analyze all the close substitutes, while on the other hand such customers who are relatively low concerned with the product they don't evaluate other alternatives. So, when the perceived risk of buying a product can vary with the level of the customer's involvement with that purchase. (Zaichkowsky, 1985). It also described by Social judgment theory that, "involvement restrained the outcome on buyer approach". Expansion possibility model (EPM) point out that the participation of customer is associated with the level of commitment to consumers. Social networking websites give a chance to both brands and customers that they have to place the loaded effective points about that product or brand that may be easily accessible (Edelman, 2007) and for the investigator to comparatively modestly mark out such WOM activity and contents (Sarwar et al., 2018; Trusov et al., 2009). The data and the information of this sort are changed over into considerably more definitive when this matches with benefit making on the web activity of customers (Wu & Wang, 2011).

Specifically, this study examines the impact of source credibility, message appeal and brand equity on purchase intentions through EWOM in the mobiles industry (Sweeny et al., 2012). This study will also test the effect of electronic word of mouth (EWOM) as a mediator between "message source credibility, message appeal, brand equity, and purchase intention". This research will also contribute to the existing literature by explaining the "elaboration likelihood model" to study how product involvement moderates the relationship between EWOM and purchase intention (Wu & Wang, 2011).

2. Literature Review

2.1. Buyer purchase intention

How much a customer is willing to buy a certain product is called its purchase intention, whether he interested to buy a specific product or not will tell its level of involvement or tendency to buy (Dodds et al., 1991). With the emergence of social networking sites People share their experiences and discuss them online and also give ratings to certain products and brands and it's called a very influential online word of mouth, it contributes further for buyers to develop their buying intentions (Zhang & Tran, 2009). So, online WOM communications that are posted in such a catchy and interesting way are becoming most important to brands to develop their image and initiate customer's buying intentions. It is a very efficient way of information and having a huge impact on brands. (Gilly et al. 1998).

"Behavioral intention (BI) is defined as a person's perceived likelihood or subjective probability that he or she will engage in a given behavior", it is formed by the attitude of a person. So, the more a person would have a positive and liking attitude towards a brand, the more it will consider purchasing (Nia & Zaichkowsky, 2000).

2.2. Message source credibility

How we interpret the word "credibility"? Simply we can define this word credibility as "believability" We can describe the credible source as "trustworthy" that have "expertise" in their message (Self, 1996). The credibility of the source can be check by evaluating the source of a message from where it's coming either the source is expert and trustworthy. Researchers have elaborated that consumers are different from each other in terms of buying behavior and such differences of consumers' attributions will have a unique and different impact on persuasion every customer has its own thinking pattern based on its past experiences and it will also affect the creditability of information (Laczniak et al., 2001; Sen et al., 2007).

Many researchers pointed out the credibility features, but the most significant point in the current literature is 'source' where from the information data has been received by the consumer the expertise of that source and the proficiency will be discussed (Self, 1996; Cheung et al., 2009).

On the other hand, the characteristics of the communication have combined by means of awareness of trustworthiness have gained a smaller amount of stress in the study of credibility. Summarizing the literature about message appeal as

H1: "Message Source credibility has a significant impact on consumer purchase intention".

2.3. Message appeal

According to Golan (2008) stated that the advertising message categorized in two ways either it is transformational or informational. The previous studies described that the ads are more concern with the judgment about that brand or give reasons to buy that brand so that customers can be aware, while the later studies argue the ads are the different types of appeals that have been developed according to the emotions or senses of the target audience (Puto & Wells, 1984).

Kotler and Keller (2008) stated that the sender of a message should be careful while designing message appeal it should consider the emotions, thinking the pattern and decision behavior of receivers

so that it can make a good position in customers' minds and make them motivated to purchase. It is essential to have any kind of effect among these promotions that make it simple for specialists and researchers to survey it basically and can accumulate their reactions eventually can give the best possible outcomes with respect to these advertisements discussed by (Rodgers & Thorson, 2000). In addition the substance that taps the feelings of the clients may have less impact on the customer and eventually the shopper may not spread word of mouth excessively but rather a valuable sane interest that demonstrates the fundamental needs of the purchaser for a more utilitarian dependent on these specialized and useful parts of the items and brands as phone (Vaughan, 1980)

H2: "Message appeal has a significant impact on consumer purchase intention".

2.4. Brand Equity

Keller divided brand equity into two categorize i.e. financial based brand equity and customer-based brand equity (Keller, 1993; Chaudhuri, 1995). As per financial prospect, it's all about the extra value in terms of money, that brand gets from its customers and overall worth of the brand in terms of its financial value and the cash flows created by the brand (Bailey & Ball, 2006). And the customer based brand equity is all about the worth and value of the brand in the customer's eye and how much extra effort a customer do for buying a specific brand. A strong brand has strong brand equity that also describes the power of a brand (Chaudhuri, 1995).

Overall marketing efforts of a company can change a product to become a brand. Customers' behavior and intention towards brand also contribute to developing strong brand equity if more customers have positive feelings towards a brand it will help the brand to become more powerful and vice versa. (Keller, 1993). Customer-based brand equity also explained as the value provided by that brand to the customers and consumer perceived it for their purchasing (Park & Srinivasan, 1994).

So this brand or power of the brand has a strong impact on customer's purchase intentions (Reynolds & Phillips 2005).

H3: "Brand equity has a significant impact on consumer purchase intention".

2.5. Electronic word-of-mouth

As described earlier WOM is a medium of person to person communication regards some product or brand and it has a high impact on overall brand performance, this is because people have more faith and trust in the non-commercial intent of advertising and they believe the WOM is more credible than traditional advertisement as discussed in the study (Herr et al., 1991; Harrison-Walker, 2001). WOM communication and sharing of information regarding a brand or product online have a great impact on the marketer's decisions. Any positive or negative comments or feedback about any brand and sharing it with other online is known as the electronic word of mouth (eWOM) discussed in the study (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004). These previous studies are a sign of how immense of a likely impact of e-WOM on the consumers purchasing decisions. Due to that reason, the intent or message of WOM is very important as a reference for the consumer to influence the intentions of that consumer regarding shopping due to that consumers can get information about the quality and reliability of the product and service as discussed in the study (Chevalier et al., 2006).

Some of the research studies have elaborated the effects of WOM communication on the purchase behavior of the consumer, the effects of purchase behavior through the eWOM based on openly accessible information from two most important online booksellers have been examined on the review of books that one person has experienced from the online library and tells the others about that bookseller (Chevalier & Mayzlin, 2006; Sabir et al., 2013). With the concern all literature based on the belongings of e-WOM on purchase intention of the consumer, research has not been carried out in order to explore which are the contents or dimensions are available that must influence the e-WOM and further has strong effects on consumer purchase intention with the role of moderation of product involvement.

In consequence, throughout the concern of eWOM activity, the customers can obtain a greater level of information about product judgment and about the marketers. Further they can evaluate and take part in the process of value chain and value addition and through this active role they can also influence products and as well as the prices regarding to that product or brand based on their own preferences and expectations as well as can increase the intentions of buying of other consumers and maybe their family or friends (Park & Kim, 2009).

H4: "Electronic word of mouth mediates the relationship between message source credibility and consumer purchase intention".

H5: "Electronic word of mouth mediates the relationship between message appeal and consumer purchase intention".

H6: "Electronic word of mouth mediates the relationship between Brand equity and consumer purchase intention".

2.6. Product involvement

Product involvement is described by many researchers it is the buyer preferences for any product/brand based on the unique aspects of consumer perception according to consumer's choice and such aspects can be values, utility or specific needs (Zaichkowsky, 1985; Mittal, 1995). The degree of involvement determine the in-depth process of consumer behavior by processing complexity cognitive and extensive behavior of the consumer to make their choices for that product explained in the study (Sabir et al., 2014; Chakravarti & Janiszewski, 2003; Dholakia, 1998)

Product involvement of customers towards any brand may vary from person to person and depends upon the individual's different interest and values, (Zaichkowsky, 1985; Batra & Ray, 1986; Goldsmith & Emmert, 1991)

The degree of involvement of the consumer has a direct effect on the attitude of the customer towards that product/brand and such involvement has a meddling influence on overall purchase intentions. Customers who are more involved most likely to get more information on eWOM. These clients are likewise quick to consider the data about that item or brand that they have looked into on the web, it implies they are consent to get the eWOM that dependent on sane interest about that item (Wu & Wang, 2011; Wang & Lee, 2005).

It has been observed that the high involvement content has more motivation and attention for the review of the product than the content which has a low level of involvement because they have superior abilities to process the information regarding that product or brand discussed by (Wang et al., 2014).

H7: "Product involvement moderates the relationship between the electronic word of mouth and purchase intention".

3. Theoretical Framework

Figure 1. Framework of study

4. Research Methodology

Zikmund (2003) has elaborated a number of sampling techniques including random, stratified, convenience, judgment, quota and snowball sampling. Convenience sampling is consisting of the group of people that can be easily assessed to get a response and most easily accessible members are chosen as subjects (Awang, 2012a; Davis, 2000). As electronic word of mouth advertising is the theme of investigation of this research study and is important for both academia and business world consequently, keep in view the scope, time and cost limitations 'convenient sampling technique' was employed.

"The study can be done either over a period or just one time of time, named as a cross-sectional or one-shot study, In case of the longitudinal study; the data is collected more than one time, to investigate the effect of change" (Sekaran, 2003). The one-shot study was employed; it was to collect the respondents' experience of receiving messages or some sort of ads regarding cell phone brands and how credibility and appeal of the message or equity of brand influence the purchase intention of the customer.

The unit of analysis is Individuals who experienced the information that they have received from different sources from internet websites about the mobile phones because target population of this study is the mobile phone users who got information about the cellular from eWOM online to gather our data. According to Sekaran (2003) "questionnaire is a composed arrangement of questions which are reformulated to record the appropriate responses, respondents, normally using closed-ended questions". A survey by questionnaire has favorable circumstances when there are numerous inquiries that must be gotten and the respondents are geographically scattered; along these lines, a survey review is chosen in this exploration.

5. Results

5.1. Reliability test

For checking the internal consistency reliability test are used that is also known as Cronbach alpha to test items that have developed, adapted or adopted are reliable with the data regarding respondent. "Cronbach alpha value should be greater than 0.6, means the alpha at 0.6 and greater is acceptable" (Awang, 2012a; Sekran, 2003). In this study reliability test were done the results of all variables are shown below.

Table 1. Reliability

Construct	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
MSC	4	.717
MAP	4	.787
BEQ	4	.704
EWOM	4	.715
PIN	4	.813
PINT	5	.809

5.2. Demographic

Questionnaire about demographic characteristics of the target population describe the age of the respondents, the gender of the respondents and also what was their priority of purchasing a cell phone brand after influencing the word of mouth online, they mentioned different brands and companies of a cell phone as mentioned in the table below.

Table 2. Demographic

Table Demographic			
		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	141	62.9
	Female	83	37.0
Age	18-23	93	41.5
	24-28	73	32.6
	29-34	45	20.0
	Above 34	13	.058
	Samsung	61	27.2
Cell phone brands	Nokia	40	17.8
	Sony	38	16.9
	Q mobile	35	15.6
	LG	32	14.2
	I phone	18	0.08

5.3. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive results show the values of normality of the data and also leads the number of respondents the minimum value of the items and as well maximum value, mean and standard deviation also shows the item's average and deviation. The data was normal shows the normality test in skewers that must be between -1to 1 and it is the minimum value of the items was 1 and maximum was 5 as items were measured on five points Likert scale, the values of all the variables are shown in the table below.

Table 3.Descriptive

Table Descriptive						
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
MSC	3.4888	.74410	.100	.163	-1.020	.324
MAP	3.2054	.81447	-.425	.163	-.249	.324
BEQ	3.5692	.60935	-.558	.163	.517	.324
EWOM	3.4766	.49635	-.268	.163	-.415	.324
PIN	4.1339	.72118	.063	.163	1.018	.324
PINT	3.0357	.37712	-.042	.163	1.041	.324

5.4. Correlation Matrix

In the correlations results we check the direction and magnitude of the variables with each other, to check that all variables are relating to each other or not to proceed further, in this study all the variables are highly significant that p-value is less than 0.01 except one and have positive directions all of them toward each other but our concern is toward dependent variable that is Purchase intention and all are positive and highly significant toward PINT and their magnitude are given below in the table:

Table 4.Correlation

	1	2	3	4	5	6
MSC	1					
MAP	.015	1				
BEQ	-.004	.092	1			
EWOM	.178**	.210**	.163*	1		
PIN	.055	.044	.409**	.048	1	
PINT	.285**	.388**	.406**	.431**	.284**	1

** p< .01, * p <0.05

5.5. Regression Analysis

Regressions analysis employed to test the hypothesis that these are accepted or rejected. For this study 'Linear regression analysis' is used to test the hypothesis; all values are revealed in the table.

Table 5.Regression

Model	UnStd		Std		Sig.
	B	Std. Er	B	t	
(Constant)	1.19	.167		7.114	.000**
MSC	.142	.027	.281	5.246	.000**
MAP	.162	.025	.350	6.500	.000**
BEQ	.232	.033	.375	6.966	.000**

Note. $R^2 = .368$; $\Delta R^2 = .360$; $F(3, 224) = 42.734$, $** p < 0.01$ $*p < 0.05$

MSC that is message source credibility has a significant impact on the purchase intention of the consumer t value is 5.246 more than 2 mean the hypothesis is accepted as well as the p-value is highly significant that is less than 0.01 and also support H1 that message source credibility has a significant impact on consumer purchase intention the study of (Park, Lee & Han, 2007), shopper rely on the message sender and if the sender is trustworthy it increase the intention of the consumer to purchase that particular cell phone . The Message appeal (MAP) also has a positive significant impact on the consumer purchase intention p-value is highly significant that is less than .01 and t value is greater than 2 that is 6.500, so H2 is also accepted means the message appeal that is sort of ad or communication body influence the consumer to purchase that product in this study the product was cell phone brands so the results validate the literature and previous studies (Wu & Wang, 2011). If we see in the table the beta value of Brand equity (BEQ) is more than rest of the others it is 0.375 means that have more impact on the consumer purchase intention rather than other variables support the literature for all the variables but brand equity has a high impact in fact high positive impact on consumer purchase intention, H3 is also accepted as t value is greater than 2 that is 6.966 and p-value is highly significant that is less than 0.01 , means consumer perceive the brand equity of that particular brand that he wants to purchase the worth of brand that the sender send on the internet influence the consumer purchase behavior regarding that brand (Yoo & Donthu, 2001).

5.6. Mediation Result

In this study, one mediator that is EWOM was taken between three independent variables that are message source credibility, message appeal and brand equity along with a dependent variable that was purchase intention. The test was made through regression that was four steps as discussed in the study of (Baron & Kenny, 1986; Wu & Zumbo, 2008). The results regarding mediator are given below.

Table 6. Mediation

Steps	IV	DV	R2	F Stat	B	Beta	t
1st	MSC	PINT	.368	42.734**	.142	.281	5.246
	MAP				.162	.350	6.500
	BEQ				.232	.375	6.966
2nd	MSC	EWOM	.280	28.520**	.191	.284	4.971
	MAP				.198	.322	5.600
	BEQ				.228	.278	4.832
3rd	EWOM	PINT	.542	62.499**	.544	.736	16.200
4th	MSC	PINT	.610	85.661*	.059	.116	2.613
	MAP				.076	.163	3.606
	BEQ				.132	.214	4.802
	EWOM				.436	.580	11.656

** $p < 0.01$ * $p < 0.05$

This table shows the results about mediation impact of EWOM influence between all independent and with dependent variables, all four paths for the three independent variables on the purchase intention are highly significant that p-value is less than .01 except the fourth one is that is significant path with p-value less than 0.05, now evaluate the values of B and R square of first and fourth row it can see that R^2 in first path that is 0.368 have increased in the fourth path that is 0.610 and B value in path forth decreasing down from the 1st step, in 1st step the beta values for all independent variables are 0.281, 0.350, 0.375 respectively and in 4th step these values are decreasing down that means the mediation is

happening between every independent and dependent variable. So, proposed hypothesis H4, H5, H6 has been established that EWOM is mediating the relationship between Message source credibility, message appeal, and brand equity and consumer purchase intention.

5.7. Moderation Result

Product involvement was used as a moderator in the current study and proposed that it moderates the connection of EWOM and purchase intention of the shoppers. This hypothesis (H7) was based on the study of Wu & Zumbo (2008), "it tells the procedure of running moderation analysis while using regression". The results are mentioned here.

Table 7.Moderation

Steps	IV	DV	R2	F Stat	B	Beta	t
1st	EWOM	PINT	.542	62.499	.544	.736	16.200
2nd	EWOM	PIN	.063	15.032	.363	.252	3.877
3rd	PIN	PINT	.081	19.487	.149	.284	4.414
4th	EWOM	PINT	.556	92.006	.502	.667	12.947
	PIN				.149	.284	4.414
	EWOM*PIN				.016	.139	2.694

In this table, all the values for the variables are significant that p-value is less than 0.01 or 0.05 and t value is greater than the 2 means all paths are significant. The R² value in the first step when EWOM is regressed on the purchase intentions is 0.542 and is increased in the fourth step when the moderator, EWOM and their interaction term was regressed on the consumer purchase intention that is 0.556 and it means moderation is happening in the relationship of EWOM and consumer purchase intention.

6. Discussion and Conclusion

Many research contemplates have been led to investigate the word of mouth in various settings that how they impact to additionally make the buying decisions (Harrison-Walker, 2001; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004). Present paper examines the EWOM settings in the context of mobile phone brand purchasing after influencing communication using the internet, this investigation utilizes the positive impact of EWOM to verify the effect of "message source credibility, message appeal and brand equity" on the buying intentions of consumers and product involvement construct was used as the moderator in this study.

According to the results message source credibility has a major and positive impact on the consumer buying intention so H1 is accepted and support the study of (Sen et al., 2007), its interpretation is, if consumer think that the message source is trustworthy than the word of mouth will push to purchase that mobile phone. The source has its value to urge or to change the brain of the recipient for the acquiring of the item (Chen et al, 2010).

Message appeal of the brand has also had a positive and significant impact on the consumer purchase intention, so the H2 is also accepted and also support the study of Kotler & Keller (2008), the affecting or emotional message of the ad also have a significant impact when customer receive the message and it motivate the receiver to further buy the mobile phone, depends on the mind of the consumer how they perceive that ad but when the message is coming from a credible source than the believability and the purchasing intention of the consumer increased after watching or reading the message, it also supports the study of Park, Lee& Han (2007).

Brand equity has a significant and positive impact on the purchase intention of customer in this context, so H3 is also accepted and also support the study of (Bailey & Ball, 2006), when customer indulge in word of mouth communication online regarding to mobile brands they also keep in mind the brand

equity and value of the brand, apart from the message they receive or analyze source they also take into account the equity that brand, this equity enhance the electronic word of mouth influence and as well as the purchasing of that brand support the study of (Keller & Lehman, 2006).

The next hypothesis H4, H5, and H6 were about the influence of EWOM are mediating the relationship of message source credibility, message appeal, brand equity, and consumer purchase intention, all these hypotheses are also accepted. it supports the study of, Sweeny et al. (2012) that EWOM influence is mediating the relationship of all these independent variables and the purchase intention, it means for purchasing of mobiles phones the source, message and brand equity create the electronic word of mouth and then this eWom influence make an impact on the consumer purchase intention (Wu & Wang, 2011).

Lastly the product involvement, as the moderator variable of the study, also moderates the relationship between EWOM and purchase intention. So H7 is also accepted it also support the likely hood model and social judgment theory (Sherif & Hovland, 1961) the product involvement in this context makes a good difference on the consumer purchase intention significantly, that influence of word of mouth online and product involvement enhance the consumer purchase intention according to the judgment and involvement of the product and this also support the study of (Wu & Wang, 2011).

7. Limitations and Future Recommendations

This research has thrown up many questions in need of further investigations. Further study may be conducted to check the behaviors of the public in other areas e.g. banking, tourism, retail stores, services and brands that people use in their daily routine life. Future research also require some other methodology techniques the combinations of qualitative and quantitative researches, as this study was descriptive in nature so qualitative techniques should be concern for future research such as in-depth interviews meetings with respondents and also focus group that may have some different results when verbal interviews at the point of purchasing will be made in a stable context and shows some interest of individual about the purchasing and obtaining of brands after influencing the word of mouth they receive online on internet.

There are also some limitations of the study such as data was collected from just two cities of Pakistan i.e. Islamabad and Rawalpindi the twin cities due to some time constraints in future the cities and culture of Pakistan may be the point of concern for future studies. The study also examines just positive setting of electronic word of mouth however the negative effect of word of mouth cannot be neglected.

8. Marketing Implications

As indicated by the verdict of this research the marketers can make a site in the target market country for the people where they can impart their experience to their family, companions, and relatives to influence their buying behavior through word of mouth (WOM). The level of contribution can likewise be utilized for advertisers to make their item as indicated by the minds of their clients with the goal that they can buy the item while including in the promotion of that organization. EWOM about a particular brand can be utilized in the advertisement to influence them to trust that the brand they are buying is beneficial and the value of that brand is extensive.

9. References

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